

Supporting Information

Enhanced Separation Concept (ESC): Removing the Functional Subunit from the Electrode by Molecular Design

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[ejoc201900432-sup-0001-SupMat.pdf](#)

Table of Contents

^1H -, ^{13}C -NMR (CDCl_3 , 500/126 MHz, 25 °C) and HR-ESI-MS spectra of compound (10)...	S1
^1H -, ^{13}C -NMR (CDCl_3 , 400/101 MHz, 22 °C) and HR-ESI-MS spectra of compound (11)...	S3
^1H -, ^{13}C - ^{19}F -NMR (CD_3CN , 400/101 MHz, 22 °C) and HR-ESI-MS spectra of compound (4)	S5
^1H -, ^{13}C -NMR (CD_2Cl_2 , 400/101 MHz, 22 °C) and HR-EI-MS spectra of compound (15)	S8
^1H -, ^{13}C -NMR (CDCl_3 , 400/101 MHz, 22 °C) and HR-EI-MS spectra of compound (16)...	S11
^1H -, ^{13}C -NMR (CD_3CN , 600/151 MHz, 25 °C) and HR-EI-MS spectra of compound (17)	S14
^1H -, ^{13}C -NMR (CDCl_3 , 500/126 MHz, 25 °C) and HR-ESI-MS spectra of compound (18)	S16
^1H -, ^{13}C -NMR (CDCl_3 , 400/126 MHz, 22 °C) and HR-ESI-MS spectra of compound (19)	S18
^1H -, ^{13}C , ^{19}F , HMBC{ ^{19}F } and HMQC{ ^{19}F }-NMR (Acetone- d_6 , 600/150 MHz, 25 °C) and HR-ESI-MS spectra of compound (5).....	S20
Stability of the heteroleptic complex (5)	S24

¹H-, ¹³C-NMR (CDCl₃, 500/126 MHz, 25 °C) and HR-ESI-MS spectra of compound (10)

Mass Spectrum SmartFormula Report

Analysis Info

Analysis Name N:\new acq data\GH4-24-1 001.d
 Method hn Direct_Infusion_pos mode_75-1500.m
 Sample Name Gero Harzmann, GH4-24-1
 Comment GH4-24-1, 1-10 ug / ml MeOH

Acquisition Date 06.05.2014 10:45:04

Operator hn
 Instrument / Ser# maXis 4G 21243

Acquisition Parameter

Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Set Nebulizer	0.4 Bar
Focus	Not active	Set Capillary	4500 V	Set Dry Heater	180 °C
Scan Begin	75 m/z	Set End Plate Offset	-500 V	Set Dry Gas	4.0 l/min
Scan End	1500 m/z	Set Collision Cell RF	350.0 Vpp	Set Ion Energy (MS only)	3.0 eV

Meas. m/z	#	Formula	Score	m/z	err [mDa]	err [ppm]	mSigma	rdb	e ⁻ Conf	N-Rule	z
698.2501	1	C 41 H 44 N 3 S 2 Si 2	100.00	698.2510	0.9	1.3	20.3	23.5	even	ok	1+

Mass Spectrum SmartFormula Report

Analysis Info

Analysis Name N:\new acq data\GH4-25-1 001.d
 Method hn Direct_Infusion_pos mode_75-1500 mid 3eV.m
 Sample Name Gero Harzmann, GH4-25-1
 Comment GH4-25-1, 1-10 ug/mL MeOH

Acquisition Date 08.05.2014 14:40:48

Operator hn
 Instrument / Ser# maXis 4G 21243

Acquisition Parameter

Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Set Nebulizer	0.4 Bar
Focus	Not active	Set Capillary	3600 V	Set Dry Heater	180 °C
Scan Begin	75 m/z	Set End Plate Offset	-500 V	Set Dry Gas	4.0 l/min
Scan End	1500 m/z	Set Collision Cell RF	500.0 Vpp	Set Ion Energy (MS only)	3.0 eV

Meas. m/z	#	Formula	Score	m/z	err [mDa]	err [ppm]	mSigma	rdb	e ⁻ Conf	N-Rule	z
291.5693	1	C ₃₅ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	100.00	291.5689	-0.5	-1.7	36.5	25.0	even	ok	2+
582.1302	1	C ₃₅ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	100.00	582.1304	0.2	0.4	41.7	25.5	even	ok	1+

¹H-, ¹³C- ¹⁹F-NMR (CD₃CN, 400/101 MHz, 22 °C) and HR-ESI-MS spectra of compound (4)

Mass Spectrum SmartFormula Report

Analysis Info

Analysis Name N:\new acq data\GH4-26-0 001.d
 Method hn Direct_Infusion_pos mode_75-1500 mid 3eV.m
 Sample Name Gero Harzmann, GH4-26-0
 Comment GH4-26-01, 1-10 ug/mL MeCN

Acquisition Date 08.05.2014 15:09:21

Operator hn
 Instrument / Ser# maXis 4G 21243

Acquisition Parameter

Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Set Nebulizer	0.4 Bar
Focus	Not active	Set Capillary	3600 V	Set Dry Heater	180 °C
Scan Begin	75 m/z	Set End Plate Offset	-500 V	Set Dry Gas	4.0 l/min
Scan End	1500 m/z	Set Collision Cell RF	500.0 Vpp	Set Ion Energy (MS only)	3.0 eV

Meas. m/z	#	Formula	Score	m/z	err [mDa]	err [ppm]	mSigma	rdb	e ⁻ Conf	N-Rule	z
524.1551	1	C 60 H 46 F 6 Fe N 8	100.00	524.1545	-0.7	-1.2	31.4	39.0	even	ok	2+
566.6230	1	C 65 H 46 F 3 Fe N 7 O 2 S 2	100.00	566.6223	-0.7	-1.3	36.1	45.0	even	ok	
609.0906	1	C 70 H 46 Fe N 6 O 4 S 4	100.00	609.0902	-0.4	-0.7	27.4	51.0	even	ok	

^1H -, ^{13}C -NMR (CD_2Cl_2 , 400/101 MHz, 22 °C) and HR-EI-MS spectra of compound (15)

Sample: BRT442
 3572ae#29-35 RT: 1.35-1.64 AV: 7 NL: 8.44E6
 T: + c EI Full ms [29.50-600.50]

Sample: BRT442
 3572ae#29-35 RT: 1.35-1.64 AV: 7
 T: + c EI Full ms [29.50-600.50]

m/z= 35.4-476.1

m/z	Intensity	Relative
41.0	426319.7	5.05
43.0	1102203.6	13.06
45.0	405059.9	4.80
57.1	380725.3	4.51
59.0	3098260.6	36.71
71.1	574693.0	6.81
73.1	2975139.4	35.26
75.1	369697.6	4.38
82.0	751501.6	8.91
82.9	570593.1	6.76
85.1	735914.0	8.72
87.1	562693.7	6.67
97.1	342694.3	4.06
99.1	464789.9	5.51
101.1	576936.9	6.84
107.0	586691.1	6.95
109.0	338134.1	4.01
110.1	392317.4	4.65
113.1	505541.7	5.99
114.2	601447.6	7.13
115.1	499445.7	5.92
121.1	816251.4	9.67
128.1	428845.6	5.08
129.1	384595.0	4.56
137.0	805559.9	9.55
139.0	744395.4	8.82
141.1	632957.4	7.50
142.1	347465.7	4.12
143.1	364343.3	4.32
151.0	360736.9	4.27
152.1	521005.9	6.17
153.1	1681491.7	19.93
154.1	1271677.1	15.07
155.1	757244.6	8.97
160.5	539684.3	6.40
161.4	754010.9	8.94
165.1	707745.6	8.39
166.1	340609.1	4.04
167.1	1000889.0	11.86
168.1	609683.0	7.22

Sample: BRT442

3572ae#29-35 RT: 1.35-1.64 AV: 7
T: + c EI Full ms [29.50-600.50]

m/z= 35.4-476.1

m/z	Intensity	Relative
169.1	1019675.4	12.08
171.1	402338.0	4.77
181.1	608252.4	7.21
182.1	560927.1	6.65
183.1	1169198.0	13.86
184.1	376625.6	4.46
185.1	662488.1	7.85
195.1	420540.7	4.98
196.1	412764.4	4.89
197.1	1086669.6	12.88
211.1	774669.6	9.18
213.1	591853.1	7.01
225.1	352749.1	4.18
229.1	486652.1	5.77
235.1	478839.7	5.67
239.1	429764.0	5.09
249.1	1492048.0	17.68
250.1	411421.3	4.88
251.0	368637.3	4.37
257.2	543184.6	6.44
263.1	1130071.4	13.39
265.0	687688.0	8.15
267.0	391787.6	4.64
277.2	1284277.3	15.22
278.2	356301.7	4.22
279.1	686291.9	8.13
281.0	505401.6	5.99
291.2	1368785.4	16.22
292.2	386256.6	4.58
293.1	1031603.4	12.22
295.0	831856.9	9.86
299.2	2189140.1	25.94
300.2	593550.0	7.03
307.1	1654437.6	19.61
308.1	354659.7	4.20
309.1	1670519.1	19.80
310.1	352220.9	4.17
319.2	4982150.9	59.04
320.2	1574647.7	18.66
321.1	1509773.9	17.89

Sample: BRT442

3572ae#29-35 RT: 1.35-1.64 AV: 7
T: + c EI Full ms [29.50-600.50]

m/z= 35.4-476.1

m/z	Intensity	Relative
323.1	949005.3	11.25
335.1	1633230.7	19.35
336.1	413577.9	4.90
337.1	1625915.0	19.27
338.1	376484.6	4.46
349.1	1118250.3	13.25
351.1	1072886.4	12.71
362.3	503334.0	5.96
377.1	7832607.1	92.82
378.1	2239452.4	26.54
379.1	8438808.1	100.00
380.1	2171273.7	25.73
381.1	548963.6	6.51
420.2	1250614.1	14.82
421.2	367595.4	4.36
422.2	1296667.4	15.37
423.2	383712.4	4.55

Sample: BRT442

3573ahr-cmass6#1-30 RT: 0.00-0.91 AV: 30 NL: 2.19E6
T: + c EI Full ms [401.71-434.71]

m/z= 419.71158-420.55712

3573ahr-cmass6#1-30 RT: 0.00-0.91 AV: 30

T: + c EI Full ms [401.71-434.71]

m/z= 419.71158-420.55712

m/z	Intensity	Relative	Theo. Mass	Delta (ppm)	Composition
420.18440	2133201.8	100.00	420.18424	0.38	C ₂₃ H ₃₇ Br Si

^1H -, ^{13}C -NMR (CDCl_3 , 400/101 MHz, 22 °C) and HR-EI-MS spectra of compound (16)

Sample: BRT450
 3574ae#21-28 RT: 0.97-1.31 AV: 8 NL: 2.13E6
 T: + c EI Full ms [29.50-600.50]

Sample: BRT450
 3574ae#21-28 RT: 0.97-1.31 AV: 8
 T: + c EI Full ms [29.50-600.50]
 m/z = 32.68-497.22

m/z	Intensity	Relative
40.0	141161.1	6.61
41.0	300384.4	14.07
43.1	293919.8	13.77
55.1	174901.8	8.19
57.1	657069.9	30.78
59.0	328139.9	15.37
69.1	157985.0	7.40
71.1	195559.9	9.16
73.1	312058.3	14.62
83.1	147562.4	6.91
85.1	195869.0	9.18
91.0	158588.0	7.43
97.1	112152.4	5.25
111.1	89684.3	4.20
115.1	137635.3	6.45
127.0	126238.8	5.91
128.1	169814.4	7.96
129.1	143588.6	6.73
141.1	155603.3	7.29
142.1	120394.5	5.64
143.1	145599.0	6.82
152.1	90210.5	4.23
153.1	124707.8	5.84
155.1	222867.0	10.44
161.1	99967.4	4.68
165.1	90782.4	4.25
169.1	160458.3	7.52
170.1	143480.4	6.72
171.1	142505.4	6.68
179.1	210852.5	9.88
183.1	96117.0	4.50
185.1	128944.9	6.04
194.1	301188.4	14.11
195.1	108178.0	5.07
197.1	236273.4	11.07
203.1	133955.3	6.28
213.1	438824.0	20.56
215.0	211563.8	9.91
217.1	127135.8	5.96
218.1	618520.1	28.98

Sample: BRT450
 3574ae#21-28 RT: 0.97-1.31 AV: 8
 T: + c EI Full ms [29.50-600.50]
 m/z= 32.68-497.22

m/z	Intensity	Relative
219.1	218862.5	10.25
228.1	888999.8	41.65
229.1	204188.0	9.57
230.1	349510.4	16.37
231.1	107080.9	5.02
233.1	94741.4	4.44
245.1	99210.3	4.65
247.1	164881.8	7.72
253.1	109957.3	5.15
261.1	183514.9	8.60
274.2	196533.6	9.21
275.1	115260.4	5.40
284.1	129146.6	6.05
289.1	372426.5	17.45
303.2	175273.1	8.21
331.2	2134624.4	100.00
332.2	629128.5	29.47
333.2	245104.0	11.48
345.2	110173.6	5.16
374.2	321537.6	15.06
375.2	97694.9	4.58
387.3	386900.0	18.12
388.3	136940.0	6.42
430.3	924843.4	43.33
431.3	332346.4	15.57
432.3	125837.8	5.90

Sample: BRT450
 3575ahr-cmass3#1-10 RT: 0.00-0.70 AV: 10 NL: 4.20E6
 T: + c EI Full ms [401.71-445.71]

3575ahr-cmass3#1-10 RT: 0.00-0.70 AV: 10
 T: + c EI Full ms [401.71-445.71]
 m/z= 429.97005-430.61307

m/z	Intensity	Relative	Theo. Mass	Delta (ppm)	Composition
430.30819	4201314.5	100.00	430.30840	-0.49	C ₂₇ H ₄₆ S Si

^1H -, ^{13}C -NMR (CD_3CN , 600/151 MHz, 25 °C) and HR-EI-MS spectra of compound (17)

Sample: BRT468
 3577ae#1-13 RT: 0.00-0.58 AV: 13 NL: 3.66E7
 T: + c EI Full ms [29.50-600.50]

Sample: BRT468
 3577ae#1-13 RT: 0.00-0.58 AV: 13
 T: + c EI Full ms [29.50-600.50]

m/z = 32.49-300.38

m/z	Intensity	Relative
57.1	2399995.1	6.57
128.1	3269512.5	8.94
129.1	1594889.8	4.36
141.1	1639794.5	4.49
142.1	2472676.1	6.76
143.1	1874137.9	5.13
153.1	1543543.2	4.22
155.1	2204570.8	6.03
161.0	2371714.5	6.49
170.1	5195053.8	14.21
175.1	2332281.0	6.38
203.1	3570588.0	9.77
218.1	36555667.8	100.00
219.1	5152547.4	14.10
220.1	1755258.0	4.80
274.2	7346308.8	20.10
275.2	1548795.8	4.24

Sample: BRT468
 3578ahr-cmass2#1-19 RT: 0.00-1.01 AV: 19 NL: 2.79E6
 T: + c EI Full ms [264.60-285.60]

3578ahr-cmass2#1-19 RT: 0.00-1.01 AV: 19
 T: + c EI Full ms [264.60-285.60]

m/z = 274.02632-274.30213

m/z	Intensity	Relative	Theo. Mass	Delta (ppm)	Composition
274.17477	2794472.5	100.00	274.17497	-0.74	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ S

¹H-, ¹³C-NMR (CDCl₃, 500/126 MHz, 25 °C) and HR-ESI-MS spectra of compound (18)

Mass Spectrum SmartFormula Report

Analysis Info

Analysis Name E:\lacq data for data analysis\BRT453.d
 Method 23 Direct_pos_higher.m
 Sample Name Thomas Brandl
 Comment 10ug/mL in MeCN, measured in MeOH

Acquisition Date 09.05.2018 15:07:15
 Operator Miff
 Instrument / Ser# maXis 4G 21243

Acquisition Parameter

Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Set Nebulizer	0.4 Bar
Focus	Not active	Set Capillary	3600 V	Set Dry Heater	180 °C
Scan Begin	75 m/z	Set End Plate Offset	-500 V	Set Dry Gas	4.0 l/min
Scan End	1700 m/z	Collision Energy	8.0 eV	Set Ion Energy (MS only)	4.0 eV

Meas. m/z	#	Formula	Score	m/z	err [mDa]	err [ppm]	mSigma	rdB	e ⁻ Conf	z
778.4221	1	C ₅₁ H ₆₀ N ₃ S ₂	100.00	778.4223	0.2	0.3	14.9	23.5	even	1+

¹H-, ¹³C-NMR (CDCl₃, 400/126 MHz, 22 °C) and HR-ESI-MS spectra of compound (19)

Mass Spectrum SmartFormula Report

Analysis Info

Analysis Name E:\acq data for data analysis\BRT455.d
 Method 23 Direct_pos_higher.m
 Sample Name Thomas Brandl
 Comment 10ug/mL in MeCN, measured in MeOH

Acquisition Date 09.05.2018 14:47:21

Operator Miff
 Instrument / Ser# maXis 4G 21243

Acquisition Parameter

Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Set Nebulizer	0.4 Bar
Focus	Not active	Set Capillary	3600 V	Set Dry Heater	180 °C
Scan Begin	75 m/z	Set End Plate Offset	-500 V	Set Dry Gas	4.0 l/min
Scan End	1700 m/z	Collision Energy	8.0 eV	Set Ion Energy (MS only)	4.0 eV

Meas. m/z	#	Formula	Score	m/z	err [mDa]	err [ppm]	mSigma	rdB	e ⁻ Conf	z
750.3186	1	C ₄₇ H ₄₈ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	100.00	750.3182	-0.3	-0.4	11.5	25.5	even	1+
1499.6287	1	C ₉₄ H ₉₅ N ₆ O ₄ S ₄	100.00	1499.6292	0.5	0.4	31.2	50.5	even	

¹H-, ¹³C, ¹⁹F, HMBC{¹⁹F} and HMQC{¹⁹F}-NMR (Acetone-d₆, 600/150 MHz, 25 °C) and HR-ESI-MS spectra of compound (5)

HMBC {¹⁹F}

Mass Spectrum SmartFormula Report

Analysis Info

Analysis Name E:\acq data for data analysis\BRT467.d
 Method 23 Direct_pos_higher.m
 Sample Name Thomas Brandl
 Comment 10ug/mL in MeCN undiluted

Acquisition Date 09.05.2018 14:12:43

Operator Miff
 Instrument / Ser# maXis 4G 21243

Acquisition Parameter

Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Set Nebulizer	0.4 Bar
Focus	Not active	Set Capillary	3600 V	Set Dry Heater	180 °C
Scan Begin	75 m/z	Set End Plate Offset	-500 V	Set Dry Gas	4.0 l/min
Scan End	1700 m/z	Collision Energy	8.0 eV	Set Ion Energy (MS only)	4.0 eV

Meas. m/z	#	Formula	Score	m/z	err [mDa]	err [ppm]	mSigma	rdb	e ⁻ Conf	z
524.1555	1	C 60 H 46 F 6 Fe N 8	100.00	524.1545	-1.0	-1.9	7.6	39.0	even	2+
650.7168	1	C 77 H 70 F 3 Fe N 7 O 2 S 2	100.00	650.7163	-0.5	-0.8	8.6	45.0	even	
777.2778	1	C 94 H 94 Fe N 6 O 4 S 4	100.00	777.2779	0.2	0.2	19.0	51.0	even	

Stability of the heteroleptic complex (5)

The stability of the heteroleptic complex **5** was analyzed in acetonitrile at 25 °C.

The composition of the reaction mixture was analyzed every 6 h by HPLC (reversed-phase C18 column with a gradient reaching from MeCN + 1% TFA / H₂O + 1% TFA = 50:50 up to MeCN + 1% TFA / H₂O + 1% TFA = 95:5 with a flow rate of 1 mL/min). Anthracene was added as internal standard to determine the relative concentration of **5**. Table 1 displays the ratio of complex **5** to the internal standard.

Table 1: Ratio of heteroleptic complex **5** to anthracene recorded every 6 hours.

time (h)	Percentage share of 5 relative to anthracene [%]	Normalized amount of 5
0	41.078	1
6	41.958	1.021423
12	41.534	1.011101
18	41.881	1.019548
24	41.437	1.008739
30	41.169	1.002215
36	41.578	1.012172
42	41.504	1.010371
48	40.645	0.989459
54	41.179	1.002459
60	40.455	0.984834
66	41.03	0.998831
72	40.802	0.993281
78	40.678	0.990262
84	39.306	0.956863
90	40.527	0.986586
96	40.009	0.973976
102	39.899	0.971299
108	39.982	0.973319
114	39.495	0.961464
120	35.91	0.874191
126	36.547	0.889698
132	37.705	0.917888
138	36.261	0.882735
144	32.674	0.795414
150	38.154	0.928818
156	37.797	0.920128
162	36.918	0.898729

The data set (table 1) was fitted with an exponential decay equation (see fit below) giving

$$y = -0.0617e^{\frac{x}{140.49676}} + 1.08405.$$

The slow decrease in concentration of the heteroleptic complex **5** can best be fitted with an exponential decay (red line) suggesting a half-life time of $t_{1/2} = 316$ h. It is noteworthy that the heteroleptic complex **5** decomposes mainly into an unknown compound (eluates after 25 minutes) instead of forming an equilibrium with both homoleptic relatives. The HPLC trace of the sample after 150 hours is displayed below. It is noteworthy that only the signal of the more polar homoleptic complex is clearly visible in the HPLC chromatogram while the less polar homoleptic complex elutes as broad flat band ranging from 40 to 45 minutes.

While the analysis of the unknown newly formed compound is beyond the scope of this manuscript, the HPLC-MS tool available allows to analyze its mass/charge ratio (see graph below). Interestingly, it resembles with $m/z = 644$ to the parent complex **5** ($m/z = 651$) lacking a CH_3 group. It is thus tempting to hypothesize the formation of oligomers of the complex involving the de-methylated amino-methyl group as additional coordinating site as compound responsible for the signal.

